

EFFECT OF HIGH LOST ON IGNITION (LOI) CONTENT CEMENT KILN DUST ON THE INDEX PROPERTIES OF BLACK COTTON SOIL**Salahudeen, A.B.* Usman, G. M.** Saidu, S. M.******Samaru College of Agriculture, D.A.C., Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria******Rail and Mass Transit Department., Federal Ministry of Transport, Abuja, Nigeria****ABSTRACT**

The preliminary investigation carried out on a black cotton soil shows that it falls under A-7-6 (16) using AASHTO classification and CL according to Unified Soil Classification System (USCS). The tests carried out on the cement kiln dust treated soil showed that the liquid limit of the natural soil increased from 48.2% to a peak value of 51.8% at 2% CKD treatment and thereafter decreased with higher CKD content. The plastic limit also increased from 27.2% for the natural soil to a peak value of 36.8% at 4% CKD treatment. The plasticity index value, decreases from 21.0% for the natural soil to a minimum value of 12.8% at 6% CKD content. The maximum dry density (MDD) for British Standard Light (BSL) and British Standard Heavy (BSH) compactive efforts increased to peak values of 1.66 and 1.91 Mg/m³ at 6% and 4%CKD contents respectively. The MDD for West African Standard (WAS) compactive effort increased with higher CKD content. The Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) for BSL and BSH compactive efforts increased up to 6%CKD content then decreased with higher CKD content. For the WAS compactive effort, the OMC generally decreased with higher CKD content.

KEYWORDS: Cement Kiln Dust, Black Cotton Soil, Atterberg limits, Compaction.

INTRODUCTION

The need to reduce the cost of waste disposal and the growing cost of soil stabilizers has led to intense global research towards economic utilization of wastes for engineering purposes. The safe disposal of industrial and agricultural wastes demands urgent and cost effective solutions because of the debilitating effect of these materials on the environment and the health hazards they constitute.

Expansive soils are also referred to as “black cotton soil” in some parts of the world. They are so named because of their colour and suitability for growing cotton. Black cotton soils have colours ranging from light grey to dark grey and black [1]. Black cotton soils are confined to the semi-arid regions of tropical and temperate climatic zones and are abundant where the annual evaporation exceeds the precipitation [2, 3]. Black cotton soils occur in continuous stretches as superficial deposits and are typical of flat terrains with poor drainage. The absence of quartz in the clay mineralogy enhances the formation of fine-grained soil material, which is impermeable and waterlogged [4].

The mineralogy of this soil is dominated by the presence of montmorillonite which is characterized by large volume change from wet to dry seasons and vice versa. Deposits of black cotton soil, which occupy an estimated area of 104 x 10³ km² in Northeastern Nigeria, show a general pattern of cracks during the dry season of the year. Cracks measuring 70mm wide and over 1m deep have been observed and may extend up to 3m or more in case of high deposit [5].

Cement kiln dust (CKD) or cement by-pass dust (CBPD) is the fine grained, solid highly alkaline waste removed from cement kiln exhaust gas by air pollution control devices. A typical Portland cement is manufactured by feeding materials containing appropriate proportions of lime, silica, alumina and iron into the upper end of a kiln. The mix passes through the kiln at a rate controlled by the slope of the kiln and the speed at which the kiln rotates. Burning fuel is forced into the lower end of the kiln where it produces temperatures of 1400-1650°C, changing the raw mix to a cement clinker. During this operation a small percentage of the material in the form of dust (i.e. CKD) is collected. The physical and chemical properties

of CKD can vary from plant-to-plant, depending on the raw materials used and type of collection process in the plant. However, the dust collected from the same kiln and producing the same cement type will typically have a relatively consistent composition.

The major parameters that determine CKD characteristics are the raw feed material, type of kiln operation, dust collection systems, and fuel type. Since the properties of CKD can be significantly affected by the design, operation and materials used in a cement kiln, the chemical and physical characteristics of CKD must be evaluated on an individual plant basis [6].

CKD containing high CaO content and low loss on ignition (LOI) performs best for most applications. High LOI dusts contain a higher percentage of bound water within its chemical structure and less CaO is available to react. The high LOI can also interfere with the hydration process. Several processing factors influence the chemical and physical properties of CKD. Because plant operations differ considerably with respect to raw feed, type of operation, dust collection facility, and type of fuel used, CKD from each plant can vary markedly in chemical, mineralogical and physical composition. Therefore it is important to thoroughly test CKD for any proposed application prior to use [7].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The disturbed black cotton soil samples used for this study were collected in March, 2012 at Deba (Latitude 10°13'N and longitude 11°23'E), Deba Local Government Area along Dadinkowa which is 30 km from Gombe town, the state capital of Gombe State, Nigeria.

The Cement Kiln Dust (CKD) used for this study was obtained from Sokoto Cement Factory, Sokoto, the capital of Sokoto State of Nigeria. The chemical composition of the CKD was conducted by method of Energy Dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence. The result of the chemical composition test is shown in Table 1. Laboratory tests were performed on the natural soil samples in accordance with BS 1377 (1990) [8] and on the cement kiln dust treated black cotton soil in accordance with BS 1924 (1990) [9]. These tests include, particle size distribution, Atterberg limits and compactions. The compaction tests were carried out for the natural soil and the stabilized soils (in 0, 2, 4, 6 8 and 10% CKD); using the British Standard light (BSL), West African Standard (WAS) and the British Standard heavy (BSH) energies, in accordance with the Nigerian General Specifications (1997) [10].

3kg of the soil/soil-admixture samples were mixed thoroughly with 4% of water (and the water is added at 4% for each of the compactions). The sample was then compacted into the 1000cm³ mould in three layers of approximately equal mass with each layer receiving 27 blows of 2.5kg rammer falling through a height of 300mm, for the British Standard light compaction; 10 blows of 4.5kg rammer falling through a height of 450mm, in five layers for West African Standard compaction and 27 blows of 4.5kg rammer in five layers falling through a height of 450mm, for the British Standard Heavy. The blows were uniformly distributed over the surface of each layer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Soil Identification

The results of the identification test conducted on the natural soil are summarized in Table 2.

Particle Size Distribution

The particle size analysis from hydrometer sedimentation test for black cotton soil – cement kiln dust mixtures are shown in Figure 1. On a general note, a nominal increase in the percentage fines was observed with increasing cement kiln dust content. This was as a result of the soil particles been replaced by the finer CKD particles, hence the increased finer particles.

Effect of CKD on Atterberg Limits

The variation of liquid limit of black cotton soil with cement kiln dust content is shown in Fig. 2. The introduction of cement kiln dust into the soil first caused an increase in the Atterberg limits to a peak value at 2%CKD treatment in the case of the liquid limit and 4%CKD treatment for plastic limit and linear

Shrinkage and thereafter decreased. The increase can be attributed to addition of CKD which introduced more pozzolanic substance into the specimen that required more water for hydration to be completed. The subsequent decrease can be associated with the agglomeration and flocculation of the clay particles which is as a result of exchange ions at the surface of the clay particles. The trend observed in liquid and plastic limits is in agreement with Ramzi et al. (2001) [11]. There was a general decrease in the plasticity index value from a value of 21.0% for the natural soil to a least value of 12.8% at 6% CKD treatment. [12] and [13] reported that the reduction in plasticity index with chemical treatment could be attributed to the depressed double layer thickness due to cation exchange by potassium, calcium and ferric ions. A nominal increment was observed at 8 and 10%CKD contents.

Effect of CKD on Compaction Characteristics

Maximum Dry Density

The variation of maximum dry density (MDD) of black cotton soil with cement kiln dust contents for the three compactive efforts are shown in Fig. 3.

For British Standard light (BSL) and British Standard Heavy (BSH) compactions, the MDD increased from 1.63 and 1.82Mg/m³ for the natural soil to 1.66 and 1.91Mg/m³ at 4 and 6% CKD contents respectively. This increase in dry density with addition of CKD may be due to cation exchange reactions. It could also be due to CKD occupying the void within the soil matrix and in addition, the flocculation and agglomeration of the clay particle due to exchange of ions [1, 14, 15,]. The subsequent reduction in MDD may be probably due to the fact that for any soil/admixture, there is always a water content to produce maximum strength [16]. This trend is in agreement with Ola (1991) [17], Lees et al (1982) [18] and Iorliam et al. (2012) [19]. The result of the West African Standard (WAS) compaction is in conformity with the trend of decreasing OMC with increasing MDD.

Optimum Moisture Content

The variation of optimum moisture content of black cotton soil with cement kiln dust contents for the three compactive efforts is shown in Fig.4. For BSL and BSH compactions, the OMC increased from values of 18.0% and 14.6% for the natural soil to peak values of 19.7% and 15.8% both at 6%CKD contents.

This trend is in conformity with results reported by Ola (1978) [20], Gidigasu (1976) [21] and Osinubi (1999) [16]. An explanation that was offered for this trend is that there was increasing desire for water which commensurates with the higher amount of the additives because more water was required for the dissociation of admixtures with Ca²⁺ and OH⁻ ions to supply more Ca²⁺ for the cation exchange reaction. The subsequent decrease in OMC with increase in CKD content might be due to cation exchange reaction that caused the flocculation of clay particles.

CONCLUSION

From the results of the study conducted, the following conclusions can be drawn.

- ❖ The black cotton soil is classified as A-7-6 (16) using the AASHTO classification system and CL using the USCS. This makes it geotechnically a problem soil.
- ❖ A high lost on ignition (LOI) content cement kiln dust (CKD) has no significant effect on the particle sizes of black cotton soil.
- ❖ The effect of high LOI content CKD on the Atterberg limits is most significant (for soil modification) at 10% or more.
- ❖ Generally, the chemical, mineralogical and physical composition of CKD should be thoroughly evaluated on an individual plant basis because several processing factors influence them.

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Table 1. Chemical composition of cement kiln dust

Oxide	CKD (%)
CaO	44.28
SiO ₂	7.23
Al ₂ O ₃	1.90
Fe ₂ O ₃	4.47
MgO	0.82
MnO	0.11
In ₂ O ₃	0.66
BaO	0.10
SO ₃	0.13
Lu ₂ O ₃	0.05
LOI(1000 ⁰ C)	39.28
TiO ₂	0.23
V ₂ O ₅	0.03
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.02
Y ₂ O ₃	0.54
ZnO	0.01
Rh ₂ O ₃	0.10
CdO	1.30
Re ₂ O ₇	0.21

Table 2: Properties of the natural black cotton soil

Property	Quantity
Percentage passing BS No 200 sieve	73.6
Natural Moisture Content, %	21.0
Liquid Limit, %	48.2
Plastic Limit, %	27.2
Plasticity Index, %	21.0
Linear Shrinkage, %	16.9
Free Swell, %	80.0
Specific Gravity	2.33
AASHTO Classification	A-7-6 (16)
USCS	CL
NBRRI Classification	High swell potential
Maximum Dry Density, Mg/m ³	
British Standard light	1.63
West African Standard	1.72
British Standard heavy	1.82
Optimum Moisture Content, %	
British Standard light	18.0
West African Standard	17.9
British Standard heavy	14.6
Colour	Greyish black
Dominant clay mineral	Montmorillonite

FIGURES

Fig. 1: Particle size distribution curves of combined dry and hydromrter sedimentation tests of black cotton soil-cement kiln dust mixtures

Fig. 2: Variation of Atterberg limits of black cotton soil with cement kiln dust content

Fig. 3: Variation of maximum dry density of black cotton soil with cement kiln dust content

Fig. 4: Variation of optimum moisture content of balck cotton soil with cement kiln dust

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